

YAŞAR ÜNİVERSİTESİ

*Yaşar University aims at fostering **gender equality policies** within the institution to bring **equality in scientific careers**, ensure **gender balance in decision-making** processes and bodies, and improve the integration of the **gender dimension in research and innovation**.*

Gender Equality Status Analysis

An extensive assessment of situation regarding **gender equality** both inside the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem where it is positioned.

This research has been carried out by YU in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal assessment followed the **three ERA priorities on Gender Equality*** and examined them in the context of **specific activity/service areas** inside YU through the collection of qualitative and quantitative data.

The data collection was conducted by the institution researchers, through **desk research, policy analysis, interviews, surveys and focus groups.**

Key Findings

HUMAN RESOURCES

Recruitment and hiring follow the rules set in the document for procedures and principles of academic and administrative staff which does not take gender into account.

There are **no gender sensitive recruitment protocols** or any policies to prevent gender bias, although the University is subject to the equality clauses in national labour law, regulations and the constitution.

The numbers about recruitment for both academic and administrative positions during the years 2015-2019 appear to be quite balanced.

Successful applicants to academic and administrative positions in the last 5 years

2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
✓ 186 Women	✓ 157 Women	✓ 199 Women	✓ 220 Women	✓ 190 Women
✓ 172 Men	✓ 176 Men	✓ 214 Men	✓ 223 Men	✓ 192 Men

*Council of the European Union (2015). Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area. RECH 295, COMPET 551, SOC 703

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Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

Gender distribution of administrative and academic staff per scientific fields and level (STEM disciplines)

	Academic	Administrative
School of Applied Sciences	7 Women - 6 Men	1 Woman - 2 Men
Faculty of Architecture	34 Women - 13 Men	2 Women
Faculty of Engineering	21 Women - 52 Men	2 Women - 1 Man

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE

Positive developments regarding gender equality at the institutional level are the decision of **the establishment of a gender studies/women's studies Center** which was accepted by the Board of Trustees and sent to the Turkish Council of Higher Education for approval.

In addition, **gender equality is included in the strategic plan for 2021-2027**. YU does not have a Gender Equality Plan in place yet but intends to create one.

The main challenge in the area of institutional governance is the need for more women in decision-making bodies and leadership positions.

Gendered composition of decision-making bodies and leadership positions

Senate

9 Women - 17 Men

Board of Directors

5 Women - 7 Men

Unit Heads (Directors)

8 Women - 13 Men

Deans

3 Women - 6 Men

Board of Trustees

1 Woman - 8 Men

Other (Appointment Commission)

3 Women - 7 Men

Vice Rectors

3 Men

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Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

Concerning the external institutional communication, YU lacks a general document on gender equality, while in terms of internal communication specific raising awareness training activities on gender sensitive language are missing as well as the use of gender sensitive communication within existing trainings.

RESEARCH & TEACHING

There are **no funds allocated for specific programs on gender studies** in Yaşar University, and only 3 projects focused on gender studies within the last 3 years.

However, a new Center on gender/women's studies is expected to be established, as it is in the final stage of approval by the Council of Higher Education (CoE). It will include academics from various fields and **focus on interdisciplinary research on gender and women's studies**.

Overall, the number of female project managers and principal investigators is more compared with the male one.

Principal Investigators
per gender

Share of female project managers:

Women benefit more than men from internal funds, but larger projects come from engineering departments, where project leaders are generally male researchers.

Currently, there are no policies and/or guidelines on how to integrate the gender dimension into curricula, neither gender sensitive teaching guidelines for professors and lectures.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

STUDENT SERVICES

Gender equality issues are not included into the student orientation training presentation and the academic staff orientation training.

**Students enrolled in STEM
studies in the last 3 years**

PhD: 27 Male - 19 Female

Masters: 68 Male - 75 Female

Bachelor: 1482 Male - 1079 Female

TRANSFER TO MARKET

According to the research findings, gender balance and equality are pursued in international projects, projects with NGOs, private sector and municipalities, although women researchers still face obstacles within projects involving public bodies.

INTERSECTIONALITY

The current research did not identify any measures in place dealing with gender in conjunction with other discriminations/structural inequalities.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

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Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The first part of the external assessment included an analysis of the **national legal and policy framework**. The second, focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** was implemented through a dedicated desk research and complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders. In addition to the context analysis, a **mapping** was conducted by YU to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders. The mapping comprised a focus group with internal stakeholders; a survey for external stakeholders and a Social Network Analysis.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

Gender equality is addressed within a **broader concept of anti-discrimination and equality** in various laws and acts included the Turkish Constitution.

There are several pieces of legislation promoting gender equality and non-discrimination in employment. The major piece of law governing employment is the **Turkish Labour Law 4857**.

In order to increase the participation of women in the labour market, measures such as increased childcare services and flexibility in employment forms are foreseen.

In Turkey specific legal texts and/or acts about gender equality policies in higher education **do not exist**.

In 2019, the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBİTAK) published its **policy principles for increasing the participation of women researchers in its processes**.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

No regulations are in place in terms of promoting the integration of gender as a scientific dimension in research both at national and regional level.

Requirements or standards on gender sensitive product or service production do not exist either.

The collected data show that the share of female STEM students is **higher than the males one in High School** but then it dramatically **decreases in Higher Education**.

A lighter imbalance persists also about STEM researchers.

The share of women among founders and leaders of start-ups is also particularly low (19%).

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

Overall, **39 external stakeholders** were included in the analysis which only included funded projects partnerships.

In total, **40 collaborations were counted**, the majority of them being with non-governmental organizations, governmental organisations, and other research institutions, which represent the main group of external stakeholders of YU.

Women lead 28 of the above collaborations.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

Concerning collaborations taking into account or focusing on **gender issues**, only **8 out of 40** (representing 20%) have such feature.

Based on the research on external stakeholders, **gender inequalities** are more visible in projects' **team compositions**, especially in case of public entities, in **management positions and salaries**.

The main identified potential synergies with Yaşar University to tackle inequalities included the development of joint projects on gender equality, the organization of raising awareness events and trainings and the involvement of policy makers.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, **CALIPER**.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

YU is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

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